

Recognition of finger position on curved surfaces in Braille displays

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Abstract: For the sensing and recognition of the actual finger position in the special case of curved plastic surfaces used in Braille displays, a capacitive principle has been developed employing Finite Element simulation. The simulated self-capacitance principle showed better sensitivity than the mutual capacitance principle and thus was used for the realization of a demonstrator. The according signals can be processed with a commercial electronic circuit based on charge transfer technology. Sensitivity and resolution allow the recognition of finger position even at high finger velocity, i.e. reading speed of experienced blind Braille readers. In the experimental set-up, a finger even at distances of some ten millimeters could be detected, thus opening the possibility of gesture recognition in the future.

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I. Introduction

The recognition of finger movements on flat glass surfaces of touchscreen displays is an established technology. However, this technology cannot be directly employed on curved plastic surfaces which are used e.g., for active Braille displays. Such Braille displays are important support tools for blind or visually impaired people [1]. Linear active Braille displays generate text segments line by line. For single-line displays the next line is generated as soon as the index (reading) finger reaches the end of the line [2]. Therefore, to make reading with Braille displays easier for blind people, it is desirable to recognize the index finger automatically in order to improve the control of the Braille display by the user. According to the world health organization (WHO) there are more than 30 Mio blind people worldwide. This underlines the importance of improving the use of active Braille displays to allow blind people to participate better in society.

In this project, a technique was developed with which suitable sensors can be integrated into single keys of active Braille displays. As proof-of-concept sensor-electrodes were placed below the curved keys of Braille displays of the German company Help Tech [3] and tested at reading speeds of experienced, fast reading blind persons. This short paper summarizes the most important findings, partially already published in [4].

II. Methods

II.1 FEM modelling of capacitive signals

In principle, two different capacitive sensing set-ups are used for finger position sensing: self-sensing and mutual capacitance effect. While in self-sensing the finger itself forms the counter electrode, in mutual capacitance sensing the finger induced change of the electric field between two neighboring electrodes is used. To select a suitable mode for a Braille display with curved surface, Finite Element

Method (FEM) was used and models of finger and keys used in typical commercial Braille reader displays were created (Fig. 1). Material data of the keys (Polyethylene), the finger and the nearby PCB were considered. The deformation of the finger when pressing on the display keys was taken into account (Fig. 1, a and b). On contrast to the real situation where the finger is moving dynamically over the Braille keys (E1-6 in Fig. 1 d), the Maxwell capacitance was simulated at different (static) positions of the finger.

Figure 1 FEM-model with finger in contact with six braille keys and printed circuit board (PCB) (ground) within an air compartment. Inserts: (a) simulated finger-braille contact surface, (b) from contact simulation extracted finger model, (c) electrode integrated braille-key model, (d) enlarged finger-braille-contact with starting position for horizontal movement over numbered keys [4]. Not shown: vertical movement

Fig. 2 shows for different vertical finger positions the difference of self-sensing and mutual capacitive sensing. Whereas for self-sensing one electrode below the key surface material was considered, for mutual capacitance sensing two electrodes with a lateral distance of 1 and 5 mm were simulated. The electrodes were placed under the curved key surface. It can be derived that self-sensing provides much larger capacitance values und differences. The same trend was observed at different horizontal finger

positions. Simulations showed that it is sufficient to use only every 2nd key for finger position recognition. Additionally, it was proved by electrical circuit model simulation that the voltage drop at a simulated (static) self-capacitance is sufficient for a commercial read-out electronics such as CapTIvate™, Texas Instruments Inc. which uses the so-called ‘charge-transfer technology’.

Figure 2 Simulated capacitances as function of vertical finger position above the Braille keys. In case of self-capacitance (left) different distances to the PCB (ground) were simulated. In case of mutual capacitance (right) 5 mm electrode distance provides considerably larger signals than 1 mm. The relative change is calculated to the position 10 mm.

II.2 Sensor implementation

To prove the simulation results a demonstrator was realized as shown in Fig.3: One electrode (self-sensing) out of a thin Cu sheet was placed in each 2nd key in the area with the 8 holes for the Braille pins. Each electrode was connected to an according electrode of the selected test kit CapTIvate™, Texas Instruments in order to use the commercial electronic and signal processing provided with the test kit Fig. 3b).

III. Results

The set-up shown in Fig. 3 was tested experimentally at different velocities of the moving finger. Results are summarized in Fig. 4 where for horizontal finger movements the signals at 2,3 cm/s and 1,8 cm/s and for vertical movement signals at 33 cm/s and 13,3 cm/s are shown. For horizontal movements finger positions could be resolved up to 5 cm/s. Vertical finger position is recognized at even higher velocity.

IV. Conclusions

Simulation and experimental results show that self-capacitive technology can be implemented to Braille keys for detecting the position of the index finger on curved surfaces of such Braille displays. Using a commercial test kit even finger position during reading of advanced, quickly reading blind persons (velocity of index finger around 5 cm/s) can be detected. For fast gesture movements a better electronic is needed. The design allows the integration in arbitrary curved plastic surfaces also in medical scenarios where control should be provided by finger movement or position.

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Figure 3 Schematic representation of a) position of the electrode, shielding and connection line in a commercial test kit with the positions of electrodes b) connection between commercial test kit and rectangular copper metal sheet electrodes c) Integration of copper metal sheet as electrode inside braille key d) 8 braille keys where every 2nd key has an integrated electrode [4].

Figure 4 Time dependences for horizontal (left) and vertical finger movements at given velocities for the set-up shown in Fig.3d (every 2nd key equipped).